
EVALUATION OF THE MULTIPLIER EFFECT OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MARKETING RESEARCH

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Abstract.

In this article, the growth of various related sectors through the development of tourism, transport infrastructure, agro-industrial complex, information and telecommunication systems, internet marketing, online booking, telephone, mobile communication and tourist-recreational complex and provision of recreation services to recreationists were considered.

Keywords.

Tourism, Marketing research, service, business, income, infrastructure, competition.

The relevance of conducting marketing research for tourism firms and companies is not only related to the problem of ensuring the success of tourism firms in the competition, but also the provision of tourism services to the population is one of the fastest growing types of business in the world today.

The growth of demand for the services of tourism firms is not only characteristic of developed countries, but also of developing countries. Because, in developing countries with high and stable economic growth rates, the increase in household income leads to an increase in the demand for tourism services. On the other hand, the rich historical monuments preserved in Uzbekistan, the acceleration of technical and socio-economic development in the country are increasing the interest of foreigners.

This requires tourism companies and firms to develop modern marketing strategies and create all the necessary conditions to overcome international competition based on their practical application.

The traditional functions of modern marketing have grown over the years, and now it has abandoned the idea of a simple exchange process based on transactions. It can no longer be considered only as a predetermined function of certain tasks. Because the number of issues included in the field of marketing of tourism services

has expanded, the scope of marketing now covers the consumer experience and life interests of customers in addition to the classic components.

The tourism industry is a complex, highly profitable industry that has a stimulating effect on the development of the main sectors of the world economy. It is a weighted network that shows Today, tourism is a catalyst of socio-economic development, and provides cultural direct and indirect support to the cultural improvement of the standard of living of the population and the development of countries and regions in the world.

The development of pilgrimage tourism is gaining importance in the economic and social life of the country. Along with the development of the economy, it will provide the employment of the local population, thereby improving the standard of living, attracting foreign tourists, introducing our country to the world, and expanding the opportunity to make a significant contribution to good works such as the preservation of our ancient cities and historical monuments.

As a result of the great attention paid to the development of tourism in the past period, Uzbekistan rose in various prestigious international ratings, and the name of the country was often mentioned in the world media.

This served to strengthen the international image of Uzbekistan, to strengthen the promotion of tourism potential.

As part of the comprehensive measures to promote Uzbekistan's tourism brand in Japan, the Embassy of Uzbekistan in Tokyo and officials of the tourism industry in cooperation with the Globe-Trotter Travel Guidebook publishing house, dedicated to the tourism potential of Uzbekistan, called "Globe-Trotter The Latest Travel Trends 2019" a magazine was published in Japanese.

In the magazine, Uzbekistan was recommended as one of the 30 most suitable countries for traveling in 2019. Also, in the magazine, a symbolic trip introducing the history of the Great Silk Road was organized by visiting the ancient cities of our country, such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Shahrisabz.

As a result of this international rating, it creates conditions for the development of pilgrimage and other types of tourism in our country. Despite the fact that Uzbekistan has a certain tourist attraction, there are problems that prevent the effective development of the tourist business. Including tourism infrastructure, level of service, etc.

Therefore, it is appropriate to conduct scientific researches that allow to identify the most promising directions of tourism development in the republic, to offer alternative development options. This can be done in the future by using

digital technologies and developing an econometric model for tourism development assessment.

In order for the funds spent by tourists to circulate in the regional economy, it is necessary to achieve the full sale of local goods and services. As a result of the sale of these goods, tourism enterprises pay their employees, and the rest is directed to the purchase of local products and services. If employees spend their wages on imported goods and services, then capital flows out of the region.

The direct or indirect combination of spending by tourists is explained by the impact on the local economy. As a rule, not all funds spent by tourists are spent in the first cycle. A certain part of it is accumulated and spent outside the territory.

The smaller the share of funds spent outside the region, the greater the multiplier effect. Maintaining tourism income within the region determines the economic closure of the region and the level of independence of the local economy. If the regional economy specializes in the production of goods and services that tourists buy, then the multiplier effect will be very significant. The more goods and services are imported from other regions, the lower the multiplier effect.

The tourism multiplier is a numerical coefficient that shows how much the gross regional product will increase or decrease as a result of an increase or decrease in tourism costs. It can be determined that through the development of tourism, the growth of various related sectors can be significantly developed, and it will allow to achieve the multiplicative (economic and social) effect. It encourages the growth of the following sectors related to tourism:

- transport infrastructure (roads and railways, air transport);
- agro-industrial complex (agriculture, food industry and catering);
- information and telecommunication systems, including internet marketing, online booking, telephone, mobile communication, etc.;
- provision of health and recreation services to tourist-recreational complexes and recreationists;
- provision of continuous energy and utility services to touristic-recreational complexes by energy and utility systems;
- the system of training, retraining and advanced training of personnel for the field of tourism in educational institutions.

It can be seen that it is urgent to determine the approaches to the evaluation of the multiplicative effect of tourism development in the region. The multiplicative process of tourism activity with the help of Buddhist resources is aimed at analyzing the impact and profitability of pilgrimage tourism in various sectors of

the economy, and is explained by cost indicators of different origins. According to the rule of determining the multiplier effect, there is a coefficient that should be multiplied by the expenses made by tourists.

The economic development of tourism, as well as its positive impact on the economy of a particular region, is reflected in the extent to which the funds spent by tourists on certain types of services are spent on environmental protection. Such attraction of funds is possible only if it is ensured that the funds spent by tourists for tourist products, basic and additional services are directed to the state budget and their spending remains directly at the discretion of the regions.

The existence of the tourist network is explained by the fact that the number and quality of these resources remain unchanged as a result of the visits of tourists for many years.

Today, D. Keynes, P. Samuelson, S. Fisher, H. Rutter, I. Krippendorf, W. Archer, S. Owen, H. Clement, D. Clark, R. Harrod, G. Hamblen, E. Hansen and other foreign scientists proposed methods and models for calculating the generalized multiplier in various sectors of the economy. According to a number of researchers, the multiplier effect of tourism is significantly more important than the effect on other types of activity, because tourism plays a decisive role in the development of other related industries.

Various multiplier models are available to estimate the impact of tourist expenditures on income, employment, and imports.

One such model was proposed by L. Bruce Archer and Charles Owen in 1971.

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^N Q_j K_{ij} V_i (1 - MPC) X_i Z_i V_i = 1 \quad n=1 \quad Nj=1$$

Here j -tourist category, $j=1, \dots, N$

i -enterprise type, $i=1, \dots, n$;

Q_j - the share of expenses made by tourists in total expenses, in j -type;

K_{ij} -the share of expenses made by tourists j -type i -type of business;

V_i -accumulation of direct and indirect incomes in the unit of expenses in the i -business type;

X_i - the share of local residents in general consumer spending i - business type;

Z_i -share X_i , from the study area.

In the process of studying the indirect impact of pilgrimage tourism on the country's economy with the help of Buddhist monuments, statistical research methods, the mathematical model of the differentiated tourism multiplier based on the theory of economic analysis of D.J. Keynes and the method of calculating the multiplier proposed by P. Samuelson and V. Nordhaus were used.

Based on the obtained data and the mentioned limitations, it was possible to calculate the indirect effect of tourism on the country's economy and the multiplier effect.13.

It should be noted that one of the problems related to the calculation of the multiplier in pilgrimage tourism is the lack of improvement in the statistics of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan. The multiplier effect of tourism is that the income generated in the future creates a "chain reaction of income" and the income received from one ecotourist is more than his expenses related to the purchase of goods and services at the ecotourism destination.

The multiplier of income from the development of tourist services varies depending on the regions (destinations). According to the researchers dealing with this indicator, the multiplier coefficient varies from 1.2 to 4.0. The nature of withholding income from tourists will depend on the economic status of the border area and the relative independence of the local economy.

Thus, it is determined that the effect of the multiplier will be greater in the area where there are full opportunities for the development of goods and services that satisfy the demand of tourists. Conversely, the more goods and services are imported from another region, the lower the multiplier effect.

REFERENCES:

1. On measures related to the rapid development of the tourism network" Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 5, 2019 No. PQ-4095.
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4755 dated June 19, 2020 "On additional measures to develop the tourism sector in strict compliance with the requirements of the enhanced sanitary and epidemiological safety regime".
3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5249 dated September 22, 2021 "On financial support for activities to be implemented in order to further accelerate large-scale construction and beautification works in Samarkand region and increase tourism potential."
3. Abramov VI Methodology otsenki innovation potentiala predpriyatiya / VI Abramov // Izvestia vysshikh uchebnykh zaseranii. Povolzhsky region. Obshchestvennye nauki. - 2012. - #4. - S.130-137.

4. Musaeva Sh.A. Usmonova D.I. Innovative marketing Study guide "TURON EDITION" Samarkand – 2021 UDK: 339.1 BBK: 65.262.2

5. S Musayeva WAYS TO IMPROVE DEMAND FORMATION AND SALES PROMOTION AT GOLDEN OIL LLC

Science and innovation 1 (A5), 215-220

6. MS Azimovna Development of innovative marketing strategies in agriculture

Web of Scientist: International Journal of Scientific Research 3 (02), 538-544

7. MS Azimovna, RN Ulugbekovna Development Conditions and Modern Trends of Business Tourism Worldwide INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY 2 (2), 63-66

8. MS Azimovna THE MAIN RESULTS OF THE LABOR PRODUCTIVITY OF THE STAFF OF THE HOTEL "BILLURI SITORA" LLC

Galaxy International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research 11(1), 348-352

9. MS Azimovna THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF MARKETING TOOLS IN INCREASING THE INTERNATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF THE TEXTILE ENTERPRISE

Science and Innovation 2 (1), 47-53

10. S Musayeva MECHANISMS OF FUNCTIONING OF LOGISTIC STRUCTURES

Science and innovation 2 (A2), 196-202

11. S Musayeva WAYS TO IMPROVE THE POLICY OF DISTRIBUTION OF GOODS IN FURNITURE PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES Science and innovation 2 (A2), 152-156

12. S Musayeva IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN THE NEED TO EVALUATE ENTERPRISES Science and innovation 2 (A2), 35-40

13. MS Azimovna Ways to Improve the Use of Marketing Information in the Assessment of "Stekloplastik" LLC American Journal of Economics and Business Management 5 (11), 338-343

14. MS Azimovna Efficiency of advertising activities of trading organizations and ways to increase IT Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities 12 (3), 93-97

15. Usmanov IA, Musayeva Sh.A. Features of marketing activities in the construction industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan. NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS Journal NX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal ISSN No: 2581 - 4230

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1, Jan. -2021

<https://repo.journalnx.com/index.php/nx/article/view/793>

16. Usmanov IA Musaeva Sh.A. Features of marketing organization in the market of construction services. Service. Scientific journal. - Samarkand. No. 2, 2021 - pp. 86-90.

17. Usmanov IA Study of the Provision of Construction Facilities with Management Personnel. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ORANGE TECHNOLOGY. Volume: 03 Issue: 9 | Sep 2021. p.31-33
<https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/2171>

18. Usmanov IA, Jumanov Sh.N. Ways to improve quality control of construction and installation works. Oriental renaissance: innovative, educational, natural and social sciences scientific journal. ISSN 2181-1784. Volume 1, Issue 10. November 2021. - P. 651-658 <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ways-to-improve-quality-control-of-construction-and-installation-works>

19. Usmanov IA Buriev HT A development strategy for the construction industry in Uzbekistan: organizational aspects of implementation. International scientific and technical journal. Real estate: economy, administration. Moscow, MGSU-No. 4 / 2021

20. Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich, RESEARCH OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF S SHARQ-UNIVERSAL-SMK LLC SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 6 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337

21. Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna, EXAMINATION OF THE INVESTMENT PROJECT OF LEASING COMPANIES SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 7 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337

22. Musaeva Sh.A. Marketing research. Textbook Publishing and creative department of "STAR-SEL" LLC. Samarkand -2023